

NATIONAL INTERESTS AND NATIONAL SECURITY RELATIONSHIP

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Annotation. This article analyzes the interrelationship and dialectical relationship of the concepts of "national interest" and "national security", which are considered fundamental categories of modern political science. The author justifies national interest as the material and objective basis (basis) of society and the state, and national security as the political and legal superstructure that protects these interests.

Keywords: National interest, national security, base and superstructure, geostrategy, hydrocarbon resources, active diplomacy, permanent interests, foreign policy, UN initiatives, enlightenment and religious tolerance.

In today's complex and rapidly changing system of international relations, the existence of each independent state and its future development depend on two important factors - national interests and their guaranteed security. As representatives of the school of political realism noted, there are no permanent friends and enemies in the international arena, but only permanent national interests. However, in an era of intensifying global competition for resources, transport and communication corridors, and geopolitical dominance, the correct understanding of national interests and the creation of a mechanism to protect them from external threats become the highest task of state governance. This article analyzes the theoretical proportionality of the concepts of national interest and national security, their internal and external directions, and the strategy of New Uzbekistan to demonstrate its national will in the global geopolitical space.

National interest is the basis (material basis), and national security is the superstructure. These categories reflect two stages of security policy, developing in interdependence and interaction: 1) the formation and expression of policy (interest). 2) the stages of its implementation. The category of interest belongs to the first, security to the second stage. In this sense, national security is a policy aimed at protecting and implementing vital national interests.

Thus, vital national interests (security objects) are the objective needs of a person/human, society and state, which are understood by the subjects of security (policy), systematized, determined in relevant political and legal documents, and are necessary and subject to protection for its existence, well-being and development in a certain historical period.

Modern international relations show that some states, organizations and citizens do not always use peaceful and diplomatic means to realize their interests.

Today, we can observe situations where new (unusual) and different forms of force are used by opposing states, established forces, and organizations to achieve and implement their goals and interests, along with the use of various types of weapons.

It is necessary to know that the basis of convincing people of the (national) interests of those forces is actually the realization of these (national) interests, which are systematically

invented (developed) through the media in order to cover up (conceal) these undesirable actions by these forces, that is, tales such as "human rights are being violated and the situation is unstable in some countries" or "democratic requirements are not being met".

These interests are based on the possession of a certain territory, water and air, natural resources, primarily hydrocarbon raw materials, routes for their transportation and means of communication, as well as the struggle to eliminate rivals (forces) that stand in the way of domination in the region and the world and in the world market.

In order to resist such actions and aggression of any kind against a nation or country, the following are considered important: solid socio-economic and political development; effective state administration; active diplomacy; guaranteed protection of vital national interests in the domestic and international arena; military power of the state.

In addition, national interests are determined based on the internal and external conditions of the state, namely, the geostrategic position and the specificity of its natural and climatic conditions, the presence and provision of natural resources, the number of the population, its religious and national composition, historical and cultural monuments, the level of development of its economy, etc.

Depending on the level of existence, national interests are permanent or temporary.

Permanent national interests include issues that serve to ensure the sustainable development of the country: protecting and preserving the population, the country's territory; protecting, preserving and rationally using human and natural resources; gradually developing an effective system of economy, science and political power.

Temporary national interests are directly or indirectly related to solving one or another issue, depending on the circumstances or situation (for example, the role of the Republic of Uzbekistan in resolving the turbulent situation in Afghanistan).

National interests can be internal and external in their direction.

Internal interests are related to solving tasks in such areas as politics, economy, social and spiritual life within the state; ensuring legality and legal order, etc.

The internal interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan include the following priority areas: democratic renewal and modernization of the country; liberalization of political and economic life, state and social construction and management; spiritual renewal of society in order to form people as mature individuals in the future; training of personnel; strengthening the growth of national well-being; strengthening social protection of the population; ensuring peace and harmony between nations and citizens in society.

External national interests include: inviolability of borders; ensuring the territorial integrity and sovereignty of the country; creating a security system to eliminate regional conflicts, in particular in neighboring Afghanistan; preventing the spread of ideas alien to us, in particular fundamentalism and religious extremism; preventing terrorism, drug trafficking and environmental disasters; strengthening foreign economic, cultural and scientific ties [1].

The current stage of the historical development of the national interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan involves geopolitical and geostrategic changes.

In terms of foreign policy dimensions, the development of the national interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan in modern conditions can be divided into three main categories:

1. The important national interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the global level are to be an active and full-fledged member of its current international relations. In this regard, the

main attention is paid to political, economic, intellectual opportunities, the power of defense policy and foreign economic opportunities;

2. The important national interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the regional level are to ensure a stable and secure international environment for the country and the region and to strengthen and develop its political and economic position in the world arena on the basis of using regional cooperation tools;

3. The important national interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the former Soviet space are to develop comprehensive relations with the CIS countries and participate in mutually beneficial integration processes of common importance between them.

At the same time, national interests are at the same time an indispensable part of the development of society, and are also a factor that forms the basis of the country's strategic tasks (goals), domestic and foreign policies.

Uzbekistan strives to build its national security in a manner that is interdependent and consistent with the regional and international security system, and in realizing its national interests, regardless of the goals, desires and wishes of foreign states or societies (forces), it always acts in a firm position and demonstrates its will to independently resolve its internal political, social and economic issues, to increase the possibilities of ensuring national harmony, general political stability and security in the country [2].

In particular, it is noteworthy that the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, at the 72nd session of the United Nations (UN) General Assembly held in September 2017, highlighted the current issues in the political arena of the world community to ensure the country's national interests. It says: "...in many cases, the focus is not on the main causes of threats, but only on combating their consequences. I believe that the root of international terrorism and extremism, along with other factors, is ignorance and intolerance. In this regard, the most important task is to form and educate the minds of people, primarily young people, on the basis of enlightenment..." [3]. Based on these sentences, the following proposals were put forward on behalf of Uzbekistan: to develop a "Convention on the Rights of Youth" and to adopt a "Resolution on Enlightenment and Religious Tolerance".

According to the official UN website (un.org), Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted his support for the draft conventions on the use of water resources in the Amu Darya and Syrdarya basins and called on the international community to prevent the complete drying up of the Aral Sea.

The source states that the issues raised by Sh. Mirziyoyev are an important factor not only for Uzbekistan, but also for ensuring the development and security of a number of regions and peoples of the world.

At the same time, vital national interests are the needs of the nation to preserve its identity as a cultural and historical unity, to protect national values, social and state institutions, to ensure sovereignty and the sustainable development of the individual, society and the state. The guaranteed protection of vital national interests from external and internal threats constitutes the content of the national security of the Republic of Uzbekistan and serves its sustainable development.

Based on the above and in conjunction with this, the main basis, that is, the objects of national security, as defined in the Concept of National Security of the Republic of Uzbekistan, are: a person - his rights and freedoms; society - his spiritual and material wealth; the state - its constitutional system, sovereignty and territorial integrity.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the concepts of national interests and national security are integral parts of a single mechanism ensuring the independence of the state. If national interests determine the material and spiritual goals of the development of the state and society, the national security system guarantees the protection of these higher goals from any external and internal hybrid attacks.

In the context of the transformation of the methods of using force in the modern world and the attempts of some geopolitical centers to realize their economic and strategic interests under the guise of "exporting democracy" or "protecting human rights", states are required to be highly political vigilant and strategic flexible.

As established in the National Security Concept of the Republic of Uzbekistan, there are three sacred objects of security: Man (his rights and freedoms), Society (his spiritual and material wealth) and the State (its constitutional order, sovereignty and territorial integrity). The global initiatives promoted by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev on international platforms - the strategy of "fighting with enlightenment" against ignorance, which is their root, rather than the consequences of threats - are considered the highest contribution of New Uzbekistan not only to protecting its national interests, but also to universal human well-being and global stability.

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